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LET'S TALK WITH AN ATM
APPLYING HUMAN COMMUNICATION THEORIES TO
HUMAN-MACHINE INTERACTION

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ABSTRACT

More and more, humans are compelled to execute transactions with artificial systems, making it imperative that such transactions be designed from the human point of view in order to make it user friendly. This paper outlines how *Speech Act Theory* and the *Theory of Communicative Action* may be applied profitably for this purpose. Austin's *Speech Act Theory* postulates the preconditions for the success of a speech act, while the *Theory of Communicative Action* asserts that a speech act is successful not only because the hearer understands what the speaker requests, but the hearer *accepts* the request as being rational and valid. A proposed framework for human-to-artificial system interaction is proposed which integrates both *Speech Act Theory* and the *Theory of Communicative Action*. *Speech Act Theory* ensures that the user understands the contents and illocutionary forces in machine-initiated speech acts while the *Theory of Communicative Action* convinces the user of the validity claims so he or she can execute the speech act. The current inadequacy of a bank ATM Speech Act sequence was analyzed and improvements proposed in the flow and screen graphics design to facilitate interaction with the user.

Keywords: human-to-artificial system interaction, Speech Act Theory, Theory of Communicative Action

INTRODUCTION

With advanced business and communications infrastructures, artificial systems that facilitate human-machine transactions have become common, be it automatic teller machines (ATM), airport check-

in counters or shopping mall direction finders. The human experience in such interactions may be described as between naturally intelligent (human) and the artificial (programmed) that has been endowed with limited intelligence through software programming. Initial studies of existing human interaction with artificial systems revealed that most of the user interfaces have their roots in ease of programming and execution without cognizance of the fact that in interactive design both the human and the artificial system need to cooperate in a sociological context.

This paper describes a pilot research on how the Theory of Speech Acts and the Theory of Communicative Action can improve human to artificial system interaction with an example of a banking Automated Teller Machine (ATM).

SPEECH ACT THEORY

While human-to-human interactions have been studied systematically through the *Theory of Speech Acts* originally propounded by (Searle, 1979) and the *Theory of Communicative Action* expounded later by (Habermas, 1981) not much has been accomplished in assessing their relevance to 'natural' interaction between humans and artificial systems. (Habermas, 1981, Auramäki, 1996). Austin's Speech Act Theory postulates that three acts together determine the success of a speech act - locutionary, illocutionary and perlocutionary [Verschueren, 2009]. Locutionary act is the mere act of uttering which, if combined with a proposition, gives rise to an illocutionary act, which is the act performed by the speaker. The perlocutionary act is what happens when the illocutionary message is perceived by the hearer, making the speech act complete. According to

Speech Act Theory, a speech act is deemed successful only if the intended perlocutionary effect is achieved. In analyzing H2M interaction, the illocutionary acts must be expressed explicitly to evoke the intended perlocutionary effects, assuring the 'performance' of speech acts in H2M communication.

THEORY OF COMMUNICATIVE ACTION

The Theory of Communicative Action asserts that a speech act is successful not only because the hearer understands what the speaker requests, but the hearer accepts the request as being rational and valid. The Theory of Communicative Action propounds four validity claims: the claim to truth, to justice, to sincerity and to power [Habermas, 1981]. A speech act is successful if the hearer subscribes to the claims to truth and justice and sincerity, or to power.

On the surface, the Theory of Communicative Action does not seem to have much relevance to the design of interactive H2M systems. Firstly, most interactive artificial systems are not intrinsically rational being pre-programmed to execute instructions. Thus, the user is unlikely to challenge the validity claims of truth, justice and sincerity. Furthermore, the claim to power is evident as the machine has the capability to execute the instructions. Thus, speech act as initiated by the machine is likely to be accepted by the user unless the user does not understand its content.

A PROPOSED FRAMEWORK FOR HUMAN-TO-ARTIFICIAL SYSTEM COMMUNICATION

In the field of information systems research, numerous scholars (Auramäki & Lyytinen 1996; Schoop 1999; Janson & Woo 1995; Kuma & Becerra-Fernandez 2007) have emphasized the importance of incorporating H2H communication theories into interactive machine systems so users can easily transact with them. There are many variations of H2H communication theories, but the two most influential ones - Speech Act Theory and Theory of Communicative Action - will be explored for their relevance to interactive machine systems.

Many researchers have reported on the application of the two theories to information systems. (Ljungberg & Holm, 1996; Suchman 1994) claimed that the Theory of Communicative Action is superior to Speech Act Theory in H2H communication. However they questioned the applicability of Habermas' validity claims in H2M communication. There are other researchers who prefer instead to integrate both theories. For instance, (Auramäki & Lyytinen, 1996) proposed to embellish speech act with Habermas' validity claims for the design of information systems. Similarly, (Schoop, 1999) is of the opinion that both theories are different aspects of speech act which can be integrated to develop a framework for communication analysis in information systems.

Both the works of Auramäki & Lyytinen and Schoop model communication patterns for information systems to facilitate communication between humans, in which the speaker is intent on the hearer understanding the communication. In this sense, Habermas' theory is more relevant. However, as an interactive artificial system seeks to influence a rational hearer to accept its speech act, the system needs to convince the hearer of facts, assertions, commitments and promises, or to request the hearer to supply information or to make selections. Thus, Speech Act Theory's perlocutionary act, which measures the success of a speech act, is more relevant to interactive artificial systems.

The proposed framework for ideal H2M interaction integrates both Speech Act Theory and the Theory of Communicative Action. Speech Act Theory ensures that the user understands the contents and illocutionary forces in machine-initiated speech acts while the Theory of Communicative Action convinces the user of the validity claims so he or she can execute the intended perlocutionary act.

A PILOT IMPLEMENTATION OF THE PROPOSED H2M COMMUNICATION FRAMEWORK

The proposed ideal H2M framework will be validated against the ubiquitous bank ATM, operated by the Post Office Savings Bank (POSBank), the bank with the largest ATM network in Singapore. The Speech Act sequence for an ATM is shown in Figure 1

Figure 1. Existing interaction flow of ATM. Circles show the issues with the current ATMs discussed in the section following

ISSUES WITH THE CURRENT ATM S

Firstly, under the “service menu” for quick cash withdrawal is “\$50”, “100”, “\$1000”. As the verb “withdraw” is missing, the propositional content is vague. Likewise many users have no idea of the propositional content of “My ATM” which personalizes a user’s preferences for faster processing. Therefore, speech bubbles are proposed to communicate the propositional contents.

Secondly, speech act 8 “Minimum withdrawal is \$20” is an indirect speech act. Its secondary illocutionary force is an assertive (to inform the user that the minimum amount one can withdraw is \$20) while the real intended objective is a directive to the user to withdraw more than \$20. Because some users may take some time to understand the intended objective, delays are common.

Lastly, the ATM cannot dispense cash either because an invalid amount was punched in or because it had run out of certain cash denominations. Presently, the ATM only informs the user of this only after 3 speech acts (insert card, enter PIN, select account). Therefore, the sequence of the machine-initiated speech acts needs to be modified to inform the user as early as possible in the interaction whether his or her objective can be met. The proposed framework is used to further assess the ATM and propose improvements to it.

Proposed modifications to the current ATMs

Firstly, the ATM must be cognizant of two main types of users: mostly frequent users but also novice users. Therefore, the machine-initiated speech acts must adapt to both familiar and novice users. This is tricky, because the speech act should not have too much propositional content that frustrates familiar users but just sufficient to guide new users.

Secondly, the ATM should sense the main interest of the user, in this case, for example cash withdrawal. Thereafter, the machine-initiated speech acts need to be sequenced in such a way that the objective is realized as soon as possible. Where the ATM is unable to dispense the desired amount of cash, the user must be informed at the very start of the interaction. This is possible if the desired amount is

indicated right after choosing the ‘withdrawal’ function. The proposed sequence of speech acts is shown in Figure 2.

Thirdly, the propositional contents of all the machine-initiated speech acts must be comprehensible. For instance, cash denominations options in the “service menu” can be improved by adding the verb “withdraw” so that they are expressed as “withdraw \$50”, “withdraw \$100”, “withdraw \$1000”. As for the “My ATM” option, a speech bubble can be incorporated; the user can scroll over the speech bubble to find out more.

Fourthly, the illocutionary forces must be clear. The strength of the directives is adequate, e.g. the flashing light and beeping sound to attract the attention of the user to the appropriate slots to collect the dispensed cash and ATM card. To avoid indirect speech act, speech act 8 “Minimum withdrawal is \$20” can be re-constituted as two separate speech acts; a directive “Please withdraw more than \$20” and a supportive assertive “Minimum withdrawal is \$20”

Figure 2. Proposed sequences of speech act for an ATM. Circled area correspond to issues pointed out in Figure 1.

Lastly, the validity claims of the speech acts should be accepted by all users. As ATMs are highly sophisticated artificial systems with enhanced security features, validity claims to truth, sincerity and justice are likely to be readily accepted by the user, provided they are comprehensible. Therefore, in developing speech acts for the ATM, the comprehensibility of the propositional content and illocutionary force are crucial to the success of the user-machine interaction.

Table 1 summarizes the shortcomings and proposed improvements to the current ATM. The change of sequence of the speech acts and modification of the indirect speech act are demonstrated in Figure 2. The proposed changes make speech acts more comprehensible and thereby facilitate user - machine interaction.

Features of machine	Shortcomings of machine	Ideal Framework	
		Proposed Solutions	Principles adhered
Require validation of identity before entering withdrawal amount	Does not prioritize the main intention of user	Change sequence such that the user enters desired withdrawal amount before inserting card and entering PIN.	Consider interest of the user by quickly informing him whether his intention can be fulfilled
Insufficient propositional content of some speech acts	Difficult to comprehend, especially for novice users	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Incorporate speech bubble feature to 'My ATM' option ▪ Include the verb 'withdraw' to cash denomination options 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Cater to main users (novice users) ▪ Comprehensible propositional content
Usage of indirect speech act	Maybe difficult for some to comprehend	Modify it to become 2 separate speech acts with distinct & clear illocutionary forces	Comprehensibility of illocutionary forces
Strong directives	-	-	Comprehensibility of illocutionary forces
Validity claims well-accepted by users	-	-	Fulfillment of all validity claims

Table 1.

APPLYING VISUAL COMMUNICATION

The proposed improvements for an ATM transaction shown in Figure 2 and Table 1 are derived from the Speech Act Theory and the Theory of Communicative Action. Besides these two theories, transacting with an ATM is an interaction that requires the application of other principles of visual design such as Hick's Law and Gestalt Principles of Perception.

HICK'S LAW

Hick's Law states that the time required to make a decision is a function of the number of available options (Lidwell et al, 2003). This would mean the more the number of alternative buttons, the longer it will take for a user to decide and select the desired button. Implication of this in an ATM transaction interface is direct - do not clutter the screen with too many alternative buttons.

GESTALT PRINCIPLES OF PERCEPTION

Gestalt which means 'unified whole' and Gestalt Principles are theories of visual perception which describe how people tend to organize visual elements into groups or unified wholes when certain principles are applied. These principles are : Similarity, Continuation, Closure, Proximity, and Figure & Ground.

(<http://graphicdesign.spokanefalls.edu/tutorials/process/gestaltprinciples/gestaltprinc.htm> - 16 May 2011)

Apart from this, considerations to the application of corporate identity guidelines of the company or brand are important as well. Use of colors, typeface, logo, hierarchy of information, etc., fall under this consideration. Where there is no existing corporate identity, the interaction designers have to create effective visual communication rules that compliment the use of Speech Act Theory and the Theory of Communicative Action.

APPLICATION TO ATM

An example of how an ATM transaction interface can be designed combining the principles of human-to-human interaction and the principles of visual communication are shown in Figures 3 to 15. The sequence shown is only for a simple 'cash withdrawal' transaction.

Figure 3. Welcome page. Standard instruction on ATM prompts the customer to insert ATM card. This was preferred in order to keep the welcome page clean.

Figure 4. Request for verification of user.

Figure 5. Selection of service request. Application of Hick's Law and Gestalt Principles is evident.

Figure 6. Selection of service request. Application of Hick's Law and Gestalt Principles is evident.

Figure 7. Selection of type of account request. Introduction of icons and navigation buttons evident

Figure 8. Selection of amount request.

Figure 9. Amount selected (\$ 300). The ATM can tell them if there are insufficient funds or if it cannot dispense in lower denominations than \$ 50, etc. can occur at this point

Figure 12. In progress indication.

Figure 10. Confirmation of amount and the account. Balance amount may be shown here.

Figure 13. Declaration of the success of the operation and request to remove the ATM card.

Figure 11. Internal action starts. Assurance that the user will get the money is given through a confirmation feedback and progress scale.

Figure 14. Indication that money is dispensed as per request is through indication on the ATM housing. Print requirement query is shown before completing the transaction. Other services are introduced here since the anxiety of money transaction is completed and the customer may have time to explore the use of the ATM.

Figure 15. Before closing the transaction; query for return to home page for more transactions.

Figure 16. Confirmation of completion of transaction through salutation.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

An ideal human-to-machine (H2M) interaction should integrate both *Speech Act Theory* and the *Theory of Communicative Action*. Through *Speech Act Theory*, the user understands the contents and illocutionary forces in machine-initiated speech acts while the *Theory of Communicative Action* convinces the user of the validity of the claims of the machine. This paper propounds a blend of *Speech Act Theory* and *Theory of Communicative Action* to address human to artificial systems interaction. The inadequacies of a current bank ATM Speech Act sequence were analyzed. The ATM's main drawbacks were vague propositional content; the real intended objective being masked by indirect speech act; and users not being alerted ahead of time whether the desired transaction can be effected. The authors propose that propositional contents be unequivocally clear and designed to cater to both familiar and novice

users; indirect speech acts be avoided, and illocutionary forces and all validity claims clarified.

In order to attain an ideal human-to-artificial interaction (H2A), from a good H2M proposition the authors applied principles of visual design to produce an *integrated interaction approach* for H2A that has been applied to an ATM transaction interface design.

The next step in this research will be to test the ATM transaction screens designed using the new integrated interaction approach on users of POSB's ATM in order to validate the framework. A pilot test is being planned where a wide spectrum of users across Singapore, both male and female, young and old with different degrees of education, who are familiar with POSB transaction, will be asked to use a mocked up ATM with the new integrated ATM interface enacting one or two predetermined transaction such as cash withdrawal and cash transfer from one account to another.

Researchers will use a mix of user centred research methods to engage the selected users through observation, questionnaire and discussions in order to obtain feedback and subsequently to seed further improvements.

The proposed ideal human to artificial system (H2A) interaction for an ATM can pave the way for implementing this framework in other interactions such as automated airport check-in kiosks, train ticketing machines, etc. It is the authors' wish that users can eventually hold a 'conversation' with interactive artificial systems in a more natural way.

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